
**D-JRP7-3.1 / Resistance profiles
to biocide and antibiotics for the
200 *Listeria monocytogenes*
strains**

JRP7 - LISTADAPT

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Report of WP3 of Listadapt from ANSES Fougères

Sub-task 3.2.1 Antibiotics and biocides susceptibility profiles of *Listeria monocytogenes* (Lm) strains

We determined antibiotics and biocides susceptibility profiles based on the characterization of MICs values for 14 antibiotics and 8 biocides from a set of 206 *Lm* strains (97 food and other strains: animals, environment) ([Table 1 and 2](#)).

Fourteen Antibiotics were tested at various concentration range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$): Ampicillin (AMP, 0.015-2); Cefotaxime (CTA, 0.5-32); Ceftriaxone (CTR, 0.5-32); Chloramphenicol (CHL, 1-32); Ciprofloxacin (CIP, 0.25-32); Erythromycin (ERY, 0.06-8); Gentamycin (GEN, 0.03-4); Meropenem (MER, 0.03-1); Nitrofurantoin (NIT, 1-32); Streptomycin (STR, 2-32); Tetracycline (TET, 0.06-8); Tiamulin (TIA, 8-64); Trimetoprim/sulfamethoxazole (TRS, 0.008/0.15-1/19) and Vancomycin (VAN, 0.25-8). These MICs were determined in sensititre™ custom microplate.

Eight biocides were used in this study at various concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$): Benzalkonium Chloride 50% (BC, 0.02-20); Didecyl DimethylAmmonium Chloride 50% (DDAC, 0.98-1000); Hydrogen peroxide 3% (Hper, 9.77-10000); PolyHexaMethylene Biguanide 20% (PHMB, 0.10-100); Sodium Hypochlorite 14% (HS, 0.01-10); N-3AMinoPropyl N-Dodecylpropane-1,3diamine 30% (AMPD, 0.03-32); Peracetic acid 40% (Pac, 4.9-5000) and Ethanol 100% (EtOH, 0.4-50%).

We observe slight differences in antimicrobial susceptibility profiles between these 206 *Lm* strains originating from various ecological niches.

However, several strains may have different susceptibility to a specific antibiotic with MIC variations ranging from a factor of 4 to 16. For Five antibiotics for which epidemiological resistance thresholds (ECOFF) are known, few strains appear to be resistant to these antibiotics : 35 strains are a MIC value of 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, just one dilution above the ECOFF and one strain with a higher MIC value at 16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (05CEB711LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1) ; one strain with a MIC value (0.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) just above the ECOFF value (0.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) for Meropenem (06CEB188LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage I - CC6) ([Table 1](#)).

Moreover, there is a greater variation in MIC values for quaternary ammonium compounds (BC and DDAC) for which MICs obtained may vary with a factor of sixteen between these strains ([Table 2](#)). However, there are differences in BC susceptibility according to the strain origin as 36 *Lm* strains from another ecological niches that food product, have a lower MIC values for BC at 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ([Table 2](#)).

Table 1. Antibiotics resistance profiles of 206 Lm strains by MICs determination

	0,008	0,016	0,032	0,064	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128
AMP						25	129	52							
CTA											2	4	3	<i>197</i>	
CTR													5	<i>201</i>	
CHL										1	193	12			
CIP							4	58	123	19	2				
ERY					22	179	5								
GEN				1	12	71	77	45							
MER					134	71	1								
NIT												1		<i>205</i>	
STR							4			99	80	23			
TET					1	8	162		34				1		
TIA										1		5	53	145	2
TRS		20	177	9											
VAN								200	6						

Table 2. Biocides resistance profiles of 206 Lm strains by MICs determination

	0,01	0,02	0,03	0,1	0,4	0,6	0,8	1	1,25	1,6	2	2,5	3,1	4	5	6,25	8	10	12,5	16	20	25	32	50	62,5	100	125	156,25	250	312,5	625	1000	1250	5000	10000	
AMPD										4				158			42			2																
DDAC						158			44			3							1																	
BC					36				113			32			24								1													
PHMB							2			95			96			9				4																
Hper																										57		117		32						
HS																															1	87		118		
Pac																																11	125	70		
EtOH (%)															1				28				89		68	20										

The first line of these tables corresponding to the various antibiotic or biocide concentrations tested (µg/ml and % for EtOH) and the first column corresponding to the antibiotics (abbreviations Eucast.org) or biocides tested.

White zone corresponding to the ranges of concentrations tested (each biocide is diluted two-fold); dark grey corresponding to the concentrations not tested; the boxes become light grey when there are strains with MIC strictly higher that concentration tested (strains number in italic) or inferior or equal

that the smallest MIC value tested (strains number underlined); number in boxes corresponding to the number of strains with this MIC and the red line corresponding to the ECOFF value defined in Eucast.org.

After that, we wanted to verify the presence of several resistance genes: *tetM*; *cadA1*; *cadA2*; *bcrABC* (Table 3). The positive control for *tetM* corresponding to *Lm* strain isolated in pork meat retail during European surveys carried out 2011 with serotype 1/2c, 3c (Soumet *et al.*, 2016). For *cadA1* we used the strain *L. innocua* 62/06, for *cadA2* *L. welshimer* 49/09 and these two strains was used to positive control for *bcrABC* (Korsak *et al.*, 2019).

Table 3. List of primers

Gene	primer name	resistance	sequence 5'-3'	length primer	length gene	reference
<i>tetM</i>	F-tetM-20	Tetracycline resistance	GTGGACAAAGGTACAACGAG	20	405	(Morvan <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	R-tetM-20		CGGTAAAGTTCGTACACAC	20		
<i>cadA1</i>	cadA1-F28	cadmium resistance	CAGAGCACTTTACTGACCATCAATCGTT	28	594	(Mullapudi <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	cadA1-R27		CTTCTTCATTTAACGTTCCAGCAAAAA	27		
<i>cadA2</i>	cadA2-F28	cadmium resistance	ACAAGTTAGATCAAAAAGAGTCTTTTATT	28	590	(Mullapudi <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	cadA2-R28		ATCTTCTTCATTTAGTGTTCCTGCAAAT	28		
<i>bcrABC</i>	919-bcrABC-F22	<i>bcrAB</i> : small multidrug resistance protein family (SMR) transporters	CATTAGAAGCAGTCGCAAAGCA	22	1353	(Elhanafi <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	920-bcrABC-R24		<i>bcrC</i> : transcriptional factor	GTTTTTCGTGTCAGCAGATCTTTGA		

Today, we performed these RT-PCRs for the first 97 *Lm* strains (food strains). We found two strains with *tetM*: *Lm* 05CEB711LM (Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1) and *Lm* 11CEB458LM (Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage II - CC8). The *Lm* 05CEB711LM corresponding to the strain with a MIC value higher than 8 µg/ml for tetracycline resistance. However, *Lm* 11CEB458LM had a MIC value equal to 1 µg/ml and appears to be non-resistant to tetracycline despite having the tetracycline resistance gene *tetM*. This latter result suggests that tetracycline resistance could be due by other *tet* resistance genes or by the unexpression of *tetM* gene. Moreover, we found 30 strains with *cadA1* but no strains with *cadA2* and *bcrABC* among these first 97 strains.

We will perform RT-PCRs for the other *Lm* strains of the second panel in the coming months.

Sub-task 3.2.2 Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

From results obtained in sub-task 3.2.1, we have selected **fourteen *Lm* strains among the first 97 *Lm* strains received (Table 4):**

- with various antimicrobial profiles (MIC values) and *Lm* strains which are the most susceptible to biocides and/or antibiotics in order to have a higher probability to see an adaptation.

and

- with different ecological niches (different type of food product)

These strains have been selected to test their ability to adapt to four different biocides molecules at a sub-lethal concentration:

- DDAC : 0.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
- BC : 0.6125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
- HS : 312.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
- Pac : 156.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Table 4. Selection of 14 Lm strains with their antimicrobial MIC values (A: antibiotic MIC values; B: biocide MIC values) for adaptation at 4 biocides (red)

A

	Strains	AMP	FOT	AXO	CHL	CIP	ERY	GEN	MERO	NIT	STR	TET	TIA	SXT	VAN	
Food - RTE Dairy	05CEB711LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-008	1	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,5	0,25	>32	4	>8	64	0,03	1
	11CEB260LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage II - CC21	16LX-042	0,5	>32	>32	8	1	0,25	0,06	0,12	>32	4	1	32	0,015	1
	14SEL1687LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage II - CC37	16LX-074	0,5	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,12	>32	8	1	64	0,03	1
	IN15 - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-096	0,5	16	32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,25	>32	4	1	32	0,03	1
Food - RTE Meat and meat products	10CEB335LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage II - CC8	16LX-032	0,5	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,12	>32	4	1	64	0,03	1
	12CEB366LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage I - CC2	16LX-058	1	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,12	>32	4	1	64	0,03	1
	15SEL676LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-082	0,5	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,25	>32	4	1	64	0,03	1
Food - RTE Fish	06CEB188LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage I - CC6	16LX-011	1	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,5	>32	4	0,5	64	0,03	1
	10CEB68LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage I - CC2	16LX-031	1	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,25	>32	4	1	64	0,03	1
	10CEB588LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage II - CC121	16LX-036	0,5	>32	>32	8	2	0,25	0,25	0,12	>32	4	1	32	0,03	1
	15SEL53LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage II - CC8	16LX-079	0,5	>32	>32	8	1	0,25	0,25	0,12	>32	4	1	64	0,03	1
Food - Vegetables	06CEB656LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-015	0,5	>32	>32	8	1	0,25	1	0,25	>32	8	0,05	64	0,06	1
	12CEB1182LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage II - CC121	16LX-067	0,25	>32	>32	8	0,5	0,25	0,5	0,12	>32	4	1	32	0,03	1
	12CEB1426LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage II - CC37	16LX-068	0,5	>32	>32	8	1	0,25	0,5	0,12	>32	4	2	32	0,015	1

B

	Strains	AMPD (µg/ml)	DDAC	BC	PHMB	HPer	HS	Pac	EtOH (%)	
Food - RTE Dairy	05CEB711LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-008	8	0,6	2,5	6,25	250	1250	625	> 50
	11CEB260LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage II - CC21	16LX-042	6	1,25	2,5	1,6	250	625	625	25
	14SEL1687LM - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage II - CC37	16LX-074	6	0,6	2,5	1,6	125	625	313	25
	IN15 - Food - RTE Dairy - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-096	6	0,6	1,25	3,1	125	625	313	12,5
Food - RTE Meat and meat products	10CEB335LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage II - CC8	16LX-032	6	1,25	1,25	1,6	125	625	625	25
	12CEB366LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage I - CC2	16LX-058	6	0,6	1,25	3,1	125	1250	625	25
	15SEL676LM - Food - RTE Meat and meat products - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-082	6	0,6	1,25	3,1	125	625	313	25
Food - RTE Fish	06CEB188LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage I - CC6	16LX-011	6	0,6	1,25	1,6	62,5	625	625	12,5
	10CEB68LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage I - CC2	16LX-031	6	0,6	1,25	1,6	250	625	625	25
	10CEB588LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage II - CC121	16LX-036	6	1,25	5	1,6	125	625	625	25
	15SEL53LM - Food - RTE Fish - Lineage II - CC8	16LX-079	6	2,5	5	1,6	125	1250	625	>50
Food - Vegetables	06CEB656LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage I - CC1	16LX-015	6	0,6	1,25	1,6	125	625	625	25
	12CEB1182LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage II - CC121	16LX-067	6	1,25	5	1,6	62,5	1250	625	25
	12CEB1426LM - Food - Vegetables - Lineage II - CC37	16LX-068	4	0,6	1,25	1,6	62,5	625	625	25

This adaptation involved an exposure of these strains to 4 different biocidal solutions during 10 consecutive days with a renewal of the broth containing biocides. After that, these adapted strains were kept at -80 °C and MICs of antibiotics (14) and biocides (8) were performed. One control for each strain was carried out with 100 µl of bacterial suspension diluted (1/100) and added to 10 ml of broth without biocide during 10 days as done for the other strains exposed to biocides. This control allows to take into account the MIC variation due to broth medium. We added also a reference strain *Lm ScottA*. Results of MIC values determined after adaptation of 14 strains selected are presented by these different graphs (*Fig 1 and 2*).

Figure 1. Variation of antibiotic MIC values after biocide exposures (*: MIC strictly higher than this value)

Ceftriaxone resistance after adaptation

Chloramphenicol resistance after adaptation

Ciprofloxacin resistance after adaptation

Erythromycin resistance after adaptation

Gentamicin resistance after adaptation

Meropenem resistance after adaptation

Nitrofurantoin resistance after adaptation

Streptomycin resistance after adaptation

Tetracycline resistance after adaptation

